

ASSESSING THE NUTRITIONAL STATUS OF INFANTS BETWEEN AGES SIX MONTHS AND TWELVE MONTHS IN ONDO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE

By

OLAREWAJU, C.A
DEPARTMENT OF HOME ECONOMICS
ADEYEMI COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ONDO

&

OLURANKINSE, C.A.
DEPARTMENT OF HOME ECONOMICS
ADEYEMI COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ONDO

Abstract

This project was carried out to assess the nutritional status of infants between the ages of six months and twelve months in Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA) of Ondo State. The two primary health care centers in OWLGA, (Model Primary Health Center, Moroko and Basic Health Care Center, Better life, Ondo) were used to carry out the research work. One hundred and twenty five mothers were selected by random sampling from each of the two health care centers to make a total of two hundred and fifty mothers. The mothers were selected to answer the questions on behalf of their infants. The data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 17. The tools used were frequency counts and percentages. Incidence of wasting was calculated. Major findings revealed that 54.8% of the infants studied consumed mainly golden morn and pap, 76.8% of the infants were breast fed exclusively. It was also revealed that the infants (78%) were fed four or five times daily with 71.2% fed at two or three hours interval. 70.8% of the infants weighed between 5.0kg and 8.0kg. High wasting (88.1%) was discovered at eight months. It was therefore recommended that mothers should be educated on the adequate nutrition that should be given to their infants. Government and public sectors should organize health talks and seminars for mothers to enlighten them on adequate nutrition to be included in the diet of their infants and how to use cheap locally available proteinous food materials to meet the dietary needs of the infants and while weaning them.

Introduction

Background to the study

An infant is the very young offspring of humans. They are children between the ages of one month and twelve months (Merriam Webster online Dictionary, 2007). Tychus, (2002) opined that the first year of life is a time of phenomenal growth and development. He further stated that throughout the first year, many physiological changes occur that allow infants to consume foods of varying composition and textures.

Good nutrition is essential for the growth and development that occurs during an infant's first year of life. When developing infants are fed with the right quality and quantity of foods, their health is sustained and promoted. The earlier infantile malnutrition is detected the better for the child. When a child suffers from malnutrition before the age of eleven months and immediate action is taken to restore the child's nutritional state, such a child has a better opportunity not to suffer malnutrition. (Ojefeitimi, 2003).

Infants should be regularly monitored for normal growth because it is within the first thirty-six months of life that the child's brain attains 80% of its adult weight (Afolabi & Owolabi, 2003). Therefore, regular monitoring should begin from six months upwards when breast milk is no longer enough to meet the child's nutritional requirements. Infants' nutritional assessment provides a vital indicator as to the number of children suffering from overt and hidden nutrition. Similarly, the assessment provides the patterns of protein energy malnutrition and the specific nutrients missing in the diet (Oguntona, 2008).

Nutritional assessment of individuals can be carried out in several ways but anthropometry is the easiest, cheapest and appropriate method for assessing infants' nutritional status above six months (Christakis, 2001). Anthropometry can be used for various purposes depending on the anthropometric indicators selected. For instance weight-for-height (wasting) is useful for screening children at risk and measuring short term changes in nutritional status (Onabanjo et al 2008)

Three indices are commonly used in assessing the nutritional status of infants and children (Onabanjo et al 2008). They are:

- (i) Weight-for-age
- (ii) Length-for-age or height-for-age
- (iii) Weight-for-length or weight-for-height.

Weight for Length: Low weight for-age index identifies the condition of being underweight for a specific age. The advantage of this index is that it reflects both past (chronic) and/or presents under nutrition (although it is unable to distinguish between the two)

Height-for-Age: Low height-age index identifies past nutrition or chronic malnutrition. It cannot measure short term changes in malnutrition. For children below two years of age, the term is length-for-age. Deficit in length-for-age is referred to as stunting.

Weight-for-Age: Low weight-length helps to identify children suffering from current or acute under nutrition or wasting and is useful when exact ages are difficult to determine (Onabanjo et al 2008).

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that the nutritional requirement of infants cannot be measured by the same yardstick as for adults who are not consuming for growth. In terms of body weight, infants need large quantity of nutrients compared to adults; they also need calories that are twice or thrice higher than those of adults. Hence, this research work is set to assess the nutritional status of infants between six and twelve months of age in Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA) and proffer strategies by which nutritional status can be improved.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of this study was to assess the nutritional status of infants between six months and twelve months in OWLGA of Ondo State. Specifically, the study:

- (i) Found out the food consumption pattern of infants between ages six months and twelve months in OWLGA.
- (ii) Determined the anthropometric status (weight) of infants between ages six months and twelve months in OWLGA.
- (iii) Determined the incidence of wasting in infants between ages six months and twelve months in OWLGA.
- (iv) Suggested ways by which the nutritional status of infants between ages six and twelve months in OWLGA can be improved.

Research Questions

- (i) What is the food consumption pattern of infants between the ages of six months and twelve months in OWLGA?
- (ii) What is the anthropometric status of infants between ages six months and twelve months in OWLGA?
- (iii) What is the incidence of wasting in infants between age six months and twelve months in OWLGA?
- (iv) How can the nutritional statuses of infants between ages six months and twelve months be improved in OWLGA?

Methodology

Design of the Study

Descriptive survey and experimental research were used for the study. Descriptive design describes and interprets "what is" It elicits information on the opinions, beliefs and behaviours of the respondents without interfering with their opinions. (Isaac,2002).

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Ondo. OWLGA is one of the eighteen Local Government Areas in Ondo State. The population of OWLGA is 283,672 (census, 2006). There are twelve wards in OWLGA. They are Newtown, Odosida, Bagbe/Igunsin, Laje, Igbado, Yaba, Ilunla, Odojomu, Okerowo, Surule, Okelisa, Lekere. Farming is the predominant occupation of the inhabitants of OWLGA. There are two primary health care centers in Ondo West Local Government area. These are:

- (i) Model Primary Health Center, Moroko, Ondo
- (ii) Basic Health Center Better Life, Ondo.

Population of the Study

The population for the study was infants between the ages of six months to twelve months in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Two hundred and fifty respondents were randomly selected. One hundred and twenty five mothers were randomly selected on behalf of their infants from each health care center.

Research Instrument for Data Collection and Validation

Structured questionnaire was used to carry out the study based on extensive literature review and the research questions. The instrument was divided i.e. Sections A and B. The questionnaire was validated by three Food and Nutrition experts in Adayemi College of Education, Ondo

Administration of Instrument and Data Collection

The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents in the two selected health care centers. The non-literates were assisted in the interpretation and filling of the items by the researcher and the completed questionnaire were collected immediately.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 17. Incidence of wasting and stunting was determined using the following formular:

Stunting:

$$\frac{\text{Height of given child}}{\text{Height of a given child of that age}} \times 100$$

Wasting:

$$\frac{\text{Weight of a given child}}{\text{Weight of a given child of that age}} \times 100$$

Analysis of Result and Discussion

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents.

1.1: Percentage distribution of respondents by mother's age

Mother's Age	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 20 years	15	6.0
20-29 years	112	44.8
30-39 years	92	36.8
40-49 years	27	10.8
50 years and above	4	1.6
Total	250	100.0

1.2: Percentage distribution of respondents by child's age

Infants Age (months)	Frequency	Percentage
6-7 months	89	35.6
8-9 months	96	38.4
10-11 months	52	20.8
12 months	13	5.2
Total	250	100.0

From the above table, 5.2% of the infants were 12 months of age, 20.8% were between ages 10 and 11 months, 35.6% were between 6 and 7 months while 38.4% were between 8 and 9 months. This implies that most of the infants (74.0%) were between 6 and 9 months.

1.3: Sex Distribution of Infants.

Sex of infants	Frequency	Percentage
Male	121	48.4
Female	129	51.6
Total	250	100.0

The table above shows that 48.4% of the infants were males while 51.6% were females. This shows that there were more female infants than males.

Table 2: Mother's food preference for the infants

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
Golden morn/corn flakes	52	20.
Beans	10	4.0
Amala & ewedu	38	15.2
Egg	5	2.0
Pap	85	34.0
Breast milk alone	0	00.0
Commercial feeds	33	13.2
Others	27	10.8
Total	250	100.0

The table above shows that 2.0% of mothers give their infant egg, 4.0% beans, 10.8% prefers to give their infant other food, 13.2% prefers commercial feeds, 15.2% prefers amala & ewedu, 20.8% prefers golden morn/cornflakes while 34.0% prefers pap. This implies that some of the mothers (54.8%) prefer to give infant golden morn or pap.

Table 3: percentage distribution of the number of times the child eats daily

No of times	Frequency	percentage
Once	0	0.0
Twice	5	2.0
Thrice	10	4.0
Four times	100	40.0
Five times	95	38.0
More than five	40	16.0
Total	250	100.0

This table shows that 2.0% of the infants were fed twice daily, 4.0% were fed thrice daily, 40.0% were fed four times daily, 38.0% were fed five times daily while 16.0% were fed more than five times daily. This implies that most of the infants (78%) were fed four or five times daily.

Table 4: Percentage distribution of time interval between child meals

Interval	Frequency	Percentage
One hour	00	00.0
Two hours	71	28.4
Three hours	107	42.8
Four hours	36	14.4
More than four hours	36	14.4
Total	250	100.0

The above table shows that 14.4% were fed at four hours interval and also more than four hours interval 42.8% were fed at three hour interval while 28.4% were fed at two hours interval. This implies that most infants (71.2%) were fed at two or three hour's interval.

Table 5: Percentage distribution of child's food preference

Food	Frequency	Percentage
Breast milk	90	36.0
Commercial feeds	80	32.0
Beans	10	4.0
Amala & ewedu	25	10.0
Others	45	18.0
Total	250	100.0

It is shown in the table above that 4.0% of infants prefer beans, 10.0% prefer amala & ewedu, 18.0% prefer other food, 32.0% prefer commercial feeds while 36.0% prefer breast milk. This implies that most of the infants (68.0%) prefer breast milk or commercial feeds to other foods.

Table 6: Percentage distribution of age infants started breastfeeding

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Birth-1month	196	78.4
1month-3months	54	21.6
3months-6months	-	-
Other	-	-
Total	250	100.0

From the table above, it can be seen that 21.6% of mothers started breastfeeding their infants between one to three months while 78.4% started breastfeeding their infants from birth to one month. This implies that most mothers (78.4%) started breastfeeding from when the child was born.

Table 7: Percentage distribution of the practice of exclusive breastfeeding for six months

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	192	76.8
No	58	23.2
Total	250	100.0

The table above reveals that 23.2% of mothers did not practice exclusive breastfeeding while 76.8% practiced exclusive breastfeeding. This shows that most mothers (76.8%) practiced exclusive breastfeeding for six months

Table 8: Percentage distribution of continuation of breastfeeding after 6months.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	219	87.6
No	31	12.4
Total	250	100.0

The table above shows that 12.4% of mothers did not continue to breastfed their infant after six month while 87.6% continued breastfeeding after six months.

Table 9: Percentage distribution of the number of times the child is breastfed daily

No of time	Frequency	Percentage
Once	19	8.68
Twice	30	13.70
Thrice	84	38.36
Four times	50	22.83
More than four times	36	16.43
Total	219	100.00

It is seen from the above table that 8.68% of the infants were breastfed once, 13.7% twice, 16.43% more than four times, 22.83% were breastfed four times while 38.36% were breastfed thrice per day. This implies that many mothers (61.19%) breastfed their infants three or four times daily.

Table 10: Percentage distribution of weaning age

Age (months)	Frequency	Percentage
0-3 months	121	48.4
3-6	101	40.4
6-9	28	11.2
9-12	00	00.00
Total	250	100.0

From the above table 11.2% weaned their infants between 6 and 9 months, 40.4% weaned them between 3 and 6 months while 48.4% weaned between 0 and 3 months. This implies that most mothers (88.8%) weaned their infants between 0 and 3 months or 3 and 6 months.

Table 11: Percentage distribution of first weaning food

Food	Frequency	Percentage
Commercial feeds	77	30.80
Pap & Cray fish	90	36.00
Proteinous foods	60	24.00
Carbohydrate foods	4	01.60
Others	19	07.60
Total	250	100.0

1.6% of infants were given carbohydrate food as the first weaning food, 7.6% were given other foods 24.0% were given proteinous foods, 36.0% were given pap & crayfish while 38.8% were given commercial feeds as the first weaning food. This implies that 74.8% of infants were first weaned with pap & Cray fish or commercial feed

Table 12: Anthropometric status of the infants studied

Weight (kg)	Frequency	Percentage
4-0-5.0	22	8.8
5.1-6.0	43	17.2
6.1-7.0	34	13.6
7.1-8.0	10	4.0
8.1-9.0	20	8.0
9.1-10.0	31	12.4
Total	250	100.0

The table above shows the weight of infants between 6 months and 12 months. 8.8% of the infants weighed between 4.0 and 5.0kg, 8.0% weighed between 8.0

and 9.0kg, 12.4% weighed between 9.0 and 10.0kg, 13.6% weighed between 6.0 and 7.0kg, 17.2% weighed between 5.0 and 6.0kg while 40% weighed between 7.0 and 8.0kg. This implies that 70.8% of the infants weighed between 5.0kg and 8.0kg.

Table 13: Incidence of wasting among the studied infants

Age (months)	Frequency	Percentage	Wasting
6	7.4	6.1	82.4
7	8.0	6.3	78.8
8	8.4	7.4	88.1
9	8.9	7.1	79.8
10	9.3	7.5	80.6
11	9.6	8.0	83.3
12	9.9	8.0	80.8

From the table above, it is shown that incidence of wasting is highest (88.1%) at 8 months old.

Table 14: Mothers views on Exclusive Breastfeeding as the best for infants for six months.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	219	87.6
No	31	12.4
Total	250	100.0

From the table shown above 12.4% of mothers did not know exclusive breastfeeding is the best for their infants for six months while 87.6% were aware it is the best.

Discussion

From the findings based on demographic characteristics of the respondents, it was observed that there were more (51.6%) female infants than male (48.4%). Also, the mothers of the infants were majorly (81.6%) between 20 to 39 years with 77.2% of them married, majority of the mothers (70.0%) were educated while some 40.8% of them were engaged in trading.

It was also discovered from the findings that 54.8% of mothers preferred giving their infants golden morn or pap which does not contain all the nutrients needed by infants. Jellifee, (2001) stated that infants

Need to be given adequate nutrients for their growth. It was also discovered that 68.0% of infants preferred to take breast milk and commercial foods which are fortified with the nutrients needed by infants but due to the mother's food preference, the infants are deprived of their choice of preference.

It was also revealed that the infants (78 %) were fed four or five times daily and 71.2% of the infants fed at two or three hours interval. (See tables 3 and 4)

The findings also revealed that 78.4% of mothers started breastfeeding their infants between birth and 1month. 76.8% practiced exclusive breastfeeding (see table 7). Doyle et al, (2004) was of the opinion that from birth to about six months of age a baby's best food is the breast milk and should be continued for the whole first year of life because breast milk provides the right blend of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, mineral and calories.

This study discovered that 88.8% of mothers weaned their infants between 0 and 3 months or 3-6 months. This implies that exclusive breastfeeding for 6 months was not practiced and the infants did not get the right nutrients needed for the first six months of life. American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) and World Health Organization WHO, (2003) opined that exclusive breastfeeding is recommended for infants for the first six months of life, after which infants should receive nutritional adequate and safe complementary foods while breastfeeding continues for up to two years of age.

The weight of the infants (70.8%) was between 5.0kg and 8.0kg. It was discovered also that 87.6% of mothers were aware that exclusive breastfeeding was the best for their infants for six months but due to ignorance and other reasons they failed to practice it. 51.6% of the mothers did not know that breast milk was the best diet for their babies for 6 months and 63.2% were not aware of the weaning age to be six months while 74.4% lack the information of introducing one food at a time during weaning. From the findings, it was discovered that incidence of wasting (88.1%) was highest at 8 months. This implies that these children can die easily due to lack enough nutritious foods to promote their growth. Wikipedia the free encyclopedia (2007) explained that wasted children and stunted children were liable to die prematurely in life because vital organs never fully develop during childhood.

Conclusion

From the study carried out, it was discovered that the food consumption pattern of infants between six months and twelve months were mainly (54.8%) golden morn or pap.

The anthropometric status (weight) of infants (70.8%) were between 5.0kg and 8.0kg which is abnormal. Also the incidence of wasting was discovered highest (88.1%) at eight months old. It was also discovered that the ways by which nutritional status of infants can be improved upon are

- (1) Organizing nutritional programmes for mothers on infants diets.
- (2) Encouraging mothers to give infants adequate diet.

Thus, this study can be concluded that the nutritional status of infants between six months and twelve months in OWLGA still needs to be improved upon

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this work, the following recommendations were made with a view to improve on the nutritional status of the studied infants (Six months and twelve months) in OWLGA:

- (I) Mothers should be educated on the nutrient requirements of infants.
- (ii) Mothers should be encouraged to breastfeed their infants exclusively for six months.
- (lii) Government and public health sectors should organize seminars and health talk for mothers to enlighten them on how to prepare cheap locally available proteinous foods for weaning their infants.
- (Iv) Government should provide commercial fortified formulas at subsidized price in the case of mothers who have difficulties in breastfeeding and for weaning age.
- (V) Mothers should be enlightened on the benefits of breastfeeding.

References

- American Dietetic Association (1997). Promotion of Breastfeeding. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*. Pp. 662-666.
- Christakis, B.A (2001). The Assessment of Nutritional Status of Community: *World Health Organization Monograph. Series 53*, Geneva Switzerland.
- Doyle, Lisa. C.O & Tracy L.M (2004). Feeding Your Child for Lifelong Health: *Birth Through Age Six*: New York Bantam.
- Guitre. A. J (2001). *Applied Human Nutrition. Britain: Macmillan Press Limited*. Pp. 3-5.
- Ojefeitimi. E.O & Owolabi (2003). *Principles and Practice of Nutrition for Community Health Workers*: None Such House Publishers. Pp. 87-90.
- Onabanjo. O.O, Oguntona C.R.B & Olayiwola I.O. (2008). Field Manual for Anthropometric Measurement. *Development of Nutrition and Dietetic: University of Agriculture Abeokuta, Nigeria*. Pp.4-6.
- Queens University. A Guide To Infant Feeding: From Birth To Twenty-Four Months. [Http://www.queensu.ca/medicine](http://www.queensu.ca/medicine).
- Turner. R.E (2000). Nutrition 3rd Edition. *America Dietetic Association*. Pp 61-64.
- World Health Organization of the United Nations. (1999). *Feeding Your Child*.